

Ford's Scholarships in Yugoslavia during the Cold War: Exposure to Western Ideology and Culture

Abstract

This research paper analyzes the activities of the Ford Philanthropic Foundation in Yugoslavia during the Cold War with a special emphasis on Ford's Education Program through which a significant number of Yugoslavs had the opportunity to study and work in the United States. Using the Ford Foundation archives, this research reveals the foundation's intentions to expose influential individuals from Yugoslavia to Western ideology and culture with the goal of suppressing communist ideology at the beginning of the Cold War. With enormous financial resources and reputation among the Yugoslav population and leadership, the Ford Foundation during its ten years of intense activity in the country (1959-1969) was completely subordinated to the official foreign policy of Washington, which was based on support for an independent Yugoslavia within the communist bloc. Ford's operational activities reduced the stereotypes of Yugoslavs about the United States and greatly contributed to the cultural rapprochement of the two countries.

Key words: Ford, Yugoslavia, American scholarships.

1 FOUNDING AND ENTRY INTO THE INTERNATIONAL SCENE

Ford Foundation was established by Henry Ford and Edsel Ford in 1936 based on serving the public welfare and helping to resolve national problems through support for institutions, communities and talented individuals in the United States.¹ The official statute of the foundation regarding the distribution of funds reads: "to receive and administer funds for scientific, educational, and charitable purposes, all for the public welfare and for no other purposes".² Since the 1950s, when the foundation's assets estimated at \$474 million³, until today, the Ford Foundation is known as one of the richest foundations in the United States of America, and is

perhaps best described in Dwight McDonald's *The Ford Foundation: The Men and the Millions* book: 'it is a large body of money completely surrounded by people who want some'.⁴

After the deaths of the foundation's founders, Henry Ford and Edsel Ford in 1943 and 1947, the foundation trustees selected eight members of independent consultants to design the future of the foundation. The study committee, led by H. Rowan Gaither who later served as president of the foundation from 1953-1956, created a report consisting of five areas of action for which the Ford Foundation would provide support. It included activities for contributions to world peace and the establishment of a world order of law and justice, advancement of the economic well-being of people, strengthening educational facilities, and activities to ensure greater adherence to the basic principles of freedom and democracy.⁵ A significant trigger for the foundation's entry on the international stage was the threat of the spread of communism and the influence of the Soviet Union in various regions of the world. Because of its decisive stance from the beginning of the Cold War, Ford Foundation in some circles was known as 'front for dangerous communists', or 'foundation that sends assassins, spies and diversionists to Eastern Europe'.⁶

Although the foundation was founded by Henry Ford in 1936, its development in financial terms took place in 1947 after his death, when Ford's shares rose at an extraordinary rate. With the automobile industry booming and record sales, Ford's assets reached \$492 million in 1950, of which the foundation's liquid assets were \$68,791,847.⁷ These figures pointed to the fact that the Ford Foundation is becoming one of the largest philanthropic foundations globally and that its business is slowly moving from the domestic to the international market. The chairman of the foundation's board of directors, Henry Ford II, described the period 1949-1950 as transitional, emphasizing that the foundation, with its modest income until 1948, focused on Detroit and its institutions, while the period after opened up opportunities for national projects and entering the international arena.⁸ The foundation began to spend big money in 1950, when it gave away \$24,000,000, and has continued on a rising scale ever since.⁹ Its 1954 spending came to just short

of \$68,000,000, which is four times what the second largest foundation at that specific period, Rockefeller, normally spent in a year and ten times the annual spending of the third largest, the Carnegie Corporation.¹⁰

The position of American philanthropic foundations that have been operating all across the globe began to change after WWII and the beginning of the Cold War between Washington and Moscow, and so was the case with the Ford Foundation. From the perspective of Washington, philanthropic foundations emerged as significant players in containing the Soviet influence on the world map. In late 1947, the *External Research Staff (ERS)*, as a division of the State Department Intelligence body, was established to coordinate between the State Department and universities, foundations, and research organizations.¹¹ Soon after its establishment, *ERS* held a meeting with the leading three foundations in the United States (Rockefeller, Ford, Carnegie) to discuss future cooperation. As a result, the foundations' fellowship programs (for U.S. citizens) provided research studies to the U.S. government. They invented a new set of intelligence agents serving as a base of information for a specific country. In the case of the Ford Foundation, some of the fellows, before leaving the United States, were receiving explicit instructions from the State Department and went through interrogation on the way back.¹²

In 1950, the Ford Foundation's board elected Paul G. Hoffman as president, significantly contributing to the foundation's more vital international role. The new man was president of the Studebaker Corporation before being sent to Europe to coordinate the implementation of the Marshall Plan, adopted by Congress in 1948.¹³ In this role, Hoffman had a direct insight into the problems and needs of the states included in the US aid plan, and more importantly, he had first-hand experience of the Cold War confrontation with the Soviet Union and the dangers of the arms race. Given the dangers of the scale of the conflict, when he returned to the United States, Paul Hoffman and his aides began working on the idea of 'conditions for peace', which remained very striking to him after his experience in Europe.¹⁴ Although Hoffman did not hold on to the Foundation's presidency for long, a new leadership led by Horace Rowan Gaither, who helped set the Foundation's priorities in 1947 at the initiative of Henry Ford II and later became

president, continued to nurture the 'Conditions for Peace' project. The project was based on building relations with the Soviet Union rather than resorting to an arms race that all pointed to the possibility of a nuclear war.

In 1953, the Ford Foundation set aside \$100,000 for a Council on Foreign Relations grant to establish a study group on American-Soviet relations.¹⁵ Ford Foundation officials considered the area of Europe to be the main field of action to combat the spread of communism and combat the widespread emergence of anti-Americanism among intellectual circles in Europe at the time. In addition to Hoffman, the director of international affairs of the Ford Foundation from 1952-to 1967, Shepard Stone was credited for the internationalization of foundation activities and increased presence in Europe, where he had many years of experience in the field. In addition to his graduate studies in Germany, Stone was a correspondent for the New York Times, witnessing the changes in the social and political areas that Germany and Europe were experiencing in general.

Stone was firmly convinced of the significant role of philanthropy in the international field during the Cold War. Addressing Ford Foundation officials in 1953, Stone stressed that the Soviet Union would use every political, economic, and psychological weapon in the years to come to harm American unity and Americans' faith in free institutions, harm the Alliance of Free Nations, and harm neutral nations in their movement towards a free world. In this regard, Stone stressed that the United States should pursue a wise policy to keep the people of the so-called free world together. His particular emphasis was that the Ford Foundation could and should make a considerable contribution to the international arena. Philanthropy, according to Stone, had the opportunity to take actions that the U.S. government was not in a position to initiate or bring out.¹⁶ During this period, the Ford Foundation invested heavily in funding Congress for Cultural Freedom in Europe, whose activities and publications in various languages were very effective in Europe and elsewhere in terms of:

- a) counteracting communist influence on political thought and
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b) developing more vigorous support for democratic developments around the world.¹⁷

Between 1951 and 1960, the Ford Foundation set aside \$32.6 billion for educational programs in the United States; some \$67.5 billion was spent on public affairs and urban, regional, and youth programs; an additional \$4.8 million was set aside for economics and business studies; and \$294.7 million for hospitals and medical schools. International grants in the same period amounted to \$256.3 billion, with an additional \$97.9 million in arts, science, and behavioral sciences.¹⁸

1.1 Ford Foundation and Cultural Diplomacy

Private initiatives played a significant role in the sphere of cultural relations of the United States during the Cold War. Frank A. Ninkovich claimed that cultural relations in the United States belonged ‘in the sphere of Liberty’ unlike European methods of *realpolitik* whereas reliance upon state control is dominant.¹⁹ Unlike the Rockefeller Foundation, whose activities abroad reached a period well before the war, the Ford Foundation began its activities on the international scene immediately after World War II. Although the foundation from its establishment took a cautious stance in supporting cultural programs questioning their effectiveness (due to the inability of quantitative measurement), it has been recorded that during the 1950s, Ford’s international arts and humanities grants were based on ideological terms, weapons in the Cold War quest for the hearts and minds of men.²⁰ In terms of numbers, approximately \$10 million foundation has invested abroad for cultural projects between 1950 and 1980, while \$300 million was allocated for international studies, and \$200 million for agricultural projects.²¹ Given that Europe was in ruins after World War II and its intellectual elite was going through a dark period, many observers in America worried that Communism and Marxism could quickly become a refuge for Europeans. For this reason, cultural support, exchanges, and projects have gained importance for the Ford Foundation.

Even though the State Department had increased responsibility for cultural programs after World War II, many believed private, non-governmental actors still had many advantages. Because the State Department was the subject of excessive domestic interference, the foundation's first president Hutchins believed that privately endowed organizations could play an influential role in the field of cultural programs and serve as an initiator of building understanding and friendship among the nations of the world.²² Foundation had a variety of resources from which to choose, from publications and scholarly exchanges to art exhibits and the performing arts. The support of literary exchanges seemed to be a promising means of increasing international understanding since intellectuals contributed substantially to the political life of most foreign countries.

Methodology

This study is descriptive research that seeks to present a detailed picture of the activities of the Ford philanthropic foundation in Yugoslavia during the 1950s and 1960s. W. Lawrence Neuman defines descriptive research as "research whose primary purpose is to paint a picture using words or numbers and to present a profile, a classification of types, or an outline of steps to answer questions such as who, when, where, and how".²³ The data collection technique of this research is qualitative and the very core of this research is based on archive documents available at the Rockefeller Archive Center in New York.²⁴ The archive is the main source of primary historical materials.²⁵ Ford Foundations' archival materials documenting work from 1936 to 2006 have been moved to the Rockefeller Archive Center in New York very recently. In shedding light on the Ford foundation's activities in Yugoslavia, this study takes into account all accessible and relevant aspects of the archival material. In addition to the archives of the foundation, this study uses the archives of the State Department and the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) to examine the relationship between the US government and the foundations. In addition to other primary material such as memoirs, secondary sources are also utilized.

This study is designed as a case study, homing in on the Ford foundation as instrument of American foreign policy and cultural diplomacy in Yugoslavia, a non-aligned country at the

height of the Cold war in the 1950s and 1960s. A case study is an intensive study of a single case or a small number of cases that draws on observational data and promises to shed light on a larger population of cases.²⁶ It is highly focused, primarily because the researcher needs significant time analyzing and deeply studying the selected case or cases, and the case is viewed as providing important evidence for the argument.²⁷ In a general perspective, a case study is explained as an attempt to interpret or understand a spatially and temporally limited set of events.²⁸ George and Bennett define a ‘case’ as an instance of a class of events, and a case study as ‘the detailed examination of an aspect of a historical episode to develop or test historical explanations that may be generalizable to other events.’²⁹ The literature mentions three phases in the design and implementation of case study research: a) in the first phase, the objectives, design, and structure of the research are formulated; b) in the second phase, the case study is conducted in accordance with the design; c) finally, the researcher draws upon the findings of the case study and assesses its contribution to achieve the research objective of the study;³⁰

Using a carefully defined research design and research questions to reach the desired research objectives, this study seeks to answer the following questions: (i) what role did the Ford foundation as non-state actor have in the exercise of the American foreign policy in general and American-Yugoslav relations in particular?, (ii) What methods did the Ford foundation use in American cultural diplomacy and the prevention of the spread of communism in the case of Yugoslavia?, (iii) What role did the Ford foundation play in Yugoslavia during the period of ideological war in the 1950s and 1960s in terms of cultural rapprochement between the United States and Yugoslavia?;

2 THE MILIEU OF THE YUGOSLAV SOCIETY IN 50-60S

The period of the 1950s as the first phase is very significant for understanding the nature of the Cold War. During this period, the foundations were laid for a way of warfare between the United States and Soviet Union that included military and economic competition, as well as

ideological conflict. One of the most significant events that determined the course of the 1950s was the Tito-Stalin conflict of 1948, which remarkably shook the communist world. Until the conflict, Yugoslavia was part of the Eastern Bloc with an identical system of government modeled on Moscow. As a result of opposition to Stalin, Yugoslavia was expelled from the *CIB* (*Communist Information Bureau*) through which Stalin had control over the entire Eastern bloc. The consequences of the resolution of the *CIB* will determine the Yugoslav policy after 1948 as an independent communist state with aspirations towards the non-aligned movement. The Tito-Stalin conflict significantly affected the general atmosphere in the satellite states of the Eastern Bloc but also the general balance of power at the international level. This outcome significantly affected Yugoslavia's approach to the West and the necessary financial and numerous other resources for the country's recovery.

Yugoslavia, whose official strategy was to successfully balance the ideological war between the United States and the Soviet Union, had been considered a territory of great importance for both sides. Besides its strategic position on the map, its military was third by size in Europe at the beginning of the 1960s. Since a direct attack against Yugoslavia was not an option either for Moscow or Washington, the deployment of soft power or cultural diplomacy was crucial and the most relevant strategy for bringing the state to its block. The influences of Moscow and Washington on the people and public life in Yugoslavia weakened or strengthened depending on the circumstances, the most important of which was the Soviet exclusion of Yugoslavia from the Communist bureau.

Moscow's economic blockade towards Yugoslavia³¹ and various attempts to topple Tito merely improved his image at home and helped him obtain considerable economic and military assistance from the West.³² The Yugoslavian economy was in a difficult situation after 1948, but the structure of industrial production until the mid-1950s remained the same — focused on heavy industry that needed to produce machinery for industrial plants. Also, it is worth noting that the economy was based on agriculture, and large exports of meat and cereals caused shortages and famines in this period. After the official split of cooperation in 1948, the Soviet Union imposed an oil embargo on Yugoslavia while the supply of other imported raw materials was reduced.

Yugoslavia's plan to be self-sustaining in the oil field was part of a five-year development plan, but it could not be accomplished without more equipment necessary to establish an oil refinery. Therefore, this problem was to be resolved by a trade agreement with the United Kingdom that would allow Yugoslavia to secure its need for oil.³³ Steel production in Yugoslavia had positive growth, but to achieve a five-year plan of about 760,000 tones, aid from the West in the form of mechanization was necessary.³⁴

Also, energy production had positive growth, but part of the equipment had to be imported from Italy and Switzerland.³⁵ Taking into account the new political atmosphere, Yugoslavia was forced to seek help from the West in many fields, but at the same time, based on its orientation of the non-aligned country, had to stop too much interference in its political affairs which was indeed challenging. In the period after the expulsion from the communist bloc in 1948 and 'turning to the West', Yugoslavia succeeded to receive more than \$700 million in a form of grants, and another billion dollars in the form of military assistance from the West.³⁶ As expected, the vast majority of funds came from the United States as the leading country in the Western part of the world. After the conflict with the Soviet Union, Yugoslavia was largely dependent on financial assistance from the United States and its allies.

From the period of war activities and the liberation of the country from the Nazi occupiers (WWII) until 1948, the influence of the Soviet Union on the people and public life in Yugoslavia was widespread. With the arrival of the Communist Party to power, Soviet culture dominated the scene in Yugoslavia, including movies, literature, language, etc. This resulted in promoting and strengthening communism among the population, which for the most part, expressed its enthusiasm for socialism. It was the so-called 'Sovietization' of all aspects of life in Yugoslavia. A new hero in Yugoslavian cinemas was 'Capajev' (legendary commander of the Red Army). While watching the same movie in Belgrade in 1945, the audience arranged a standing ovation for the glorious victory of the Slavic people against German occupiers and an ovation for comrades Stalin and Tito.³⁷ However, the political confrontation between Tito and Stalin in 1948 greatly disrupted Soviet propaganda in Yugoslavia. Such developments immediately affected the

type of films shown in cinemas due to constant censorship by the Yugoslav authorities. The number of American and Soviet movies shown in Belgrade cinemas in 1949 was almost equal.³⁸ The turning point came in 1950 when Yugoslavia did not import a single Soviet movie and since the complete primacy of the cinemas' repertoires became occupied by American cinematography.³⁹ Statistics show that from 1952 to 1956 Yugoslavia imported 325 movies from the United States, 101 from the United Kingdom, 99 from France, 62 from Italy, and 33 from the Soviet Union.⁴⁰

The conflict within the communist bloc affected all spheres of relations between the two countries. In an interview with the official of the Foundation in 1950, Sinisha Tassovatz from the University of Belgrade stated that the general atmosphere in the country was comfortable, and that professional people and artists had privileges in the form of salaries and ration cards.⁴¹ Through contact with former fellows, the foundation explored the ground for re-establishing relations with scientists in Yugoslavia. According to Tassovatz, cultural contacts with Russia at the time have been in the process of a sharp decline for the past two years, and there is currently no exchange between the countries (1950).⁴² Somewhere over 100 medical students who went to Russian schools in 1947 (mostly to Moscow) all returned to continue their education at home.⁴³ The archive reveals that the Yugoslavs already in 1950 showed great hope for increased contact with the West. According to Tassovatz, individuals from Yugoslavia who had the opportunity to visit the United States showed respect for higher levels of culture and education and the conditions of ordinary people.

Yugoslavia had a strong tradition of supporting the arts, albeit under a socialist regime. The Academies of Film, Radio-Television, and Music had a very solid base for the instruction and development of qualified students in these fields. The overall picture of Yugoslav art compared to the world stage was solid, although Ford officers were not so impressed with the situation in the field, as Officer D'Arms stated in his report: 'The picture is one of activity but not

excitement; of ability but not great talent or genius; of concern but not of creative ferment'.⁴⁴ The socialist system of the state, which implies more pronounced control and censorship of the population, also greatly contributed to this. Also, the political organization of the state in the six federal republics remarkably prevented the competition and confrontation of the most talented artists because during the 1960s, in the process of decentralization of Yugoslavia, supporting art was the task of a separate republic and not the central government in Belgrade. This meant that Serbs, Croats, and Slovenes were in a more favorable position due to their pronounced tradition of art and more or less significantly better financial situation.

American culture had its first contact with Yugoslavia very early, in the period between the two world wars. Hollywood production and American movies enjoyed great popularity in Yugoslavian cinemas during the interwar period. In the abundance of movie magazines that were then published, the Hollywood magazine (contemporary magazine for film life, modern arts, sports, and world sensation) appeared in Belgrade in 1928.⁴⁵ Nearly 500 American films were imported to Serbia in 1939, and apart from them, 182 from Western Europe and 25 films from Czechoslovakia and Hungary.⁴⁶ Vucetic noted that both the end of World War II and the liberation of Belgrade were celebrated with an American film featuring the sounds of jazz - *Seranada in the Sun Valley*.⁴⁷ Traditional loyalty to American movies was interrupted in 1944 with the process of 'Sovietization' of all aspects of life in Yugoslavia.

The American movies were slowly re-introduced to Yugoslavian cinemas, music expanded, and educational exchange programs between the two countries started taking place. A significant number of foreign films have been shown annually in Yugoslavia. They regularly attracted large audiences, of which American and French films were the most popular. In the first nine months of 1955, Belgrade theaters exhibited 417 films, of which 189 were American, 58 British, 49 French, 43 Yugoslav, and 11 German.⁴⁸ The total viewership reached 7,900,000 visitors.⁴⁹ The average number of reviews of French films was about 28,000, 18,700 for American films, 18,400 for German, 17,000 for British, 15,000 for Italian, and 14,700 for

Yugoslav.⁵⁰ The most popular film in that period was the Hollywood *Shadows of the Past*, which was watched by 92,800 people.⁵¹

As early as 1951, the English language instruction program over the Zagreb Radio had many listeners.⁵² English at that time was the main second language in Zagreb, with over 400 students in the Department of English, and with all lessons, seminars and class discussions conducted entirely in English.⁵³ For this reason, as early as 1951, the Rockefeller foundation considered providing a grant to Rudolf Filipovic, a Croat in his thirties who ran an English-language radio program in Zagreb but refrained due to the political complications of obtaining American visas for Yugoslavs.

One of the ways in which Yugoslavs made contact with Western ideas, cultures, and individuals was through learning Western languages. Yugoslavia has traditionally nurtured interest and connection with Western languages. French and German were very present in Serbia, Croatia, and Bosnia and Herzegovina. However, in the mid-1950s, English was slowly becoming the main foreign language in Yugoslavia. The Yugoslav government encouraged students to learn English, especially in technical fields. At the five main universities in the country (Belgrade, Zagreb, Ljubljana, Sarajevo, Skopje) that were administered by the Board of Education under the auspices of the Ministry of Culture, there was an obvious growth of English language students.⁵⁴ During 1954, the estimated enrollment of students in English faculties at the five universities was 3,150 students, of which 1,500 were in Belgrade and 1,000 in Zagreb.⁵⁵ In that period, the Republic of Slovenia introduced English into primary school classes, using materials prepared with the help of the USIS Center in Yugoslavia. In Banja Luka, the second largest city in Bosnia and Herzegovina, English language learning was introduced in 1954, attracting 70 students.⁵⁶ The following year, that number climbed to 350 students in high school and medical high school.⁵⁷

American literature was very widespread in Yugoslav libraries. The positive mood of the public towards the materials from different fields was obvious.⁵⁸ Lecturers in Yugoslav educational institutions often used American books as teaching material, especially in the fields of history and geography. Books on the American judicial and political system have also been studied. The American Book Translation Program in Yugoslavia made a special effort to provide readers with books on aspects of American democracy and its goals. These titles included: Eisenhower's Crusade in Europe; The origin and development of the American economy; The making of democracy; Woodrow Wilson's own story; Understanding the American past; and many others. The geographical distribution of these titles was mainly concentrated in the centers of Belgrade, Zagreb, and Ljubljana.⁵⁹

In her analysis of the Americanization of Yugoslav popular culture in the 1960s, Radina Vucetic⁶⁰ claims that the 'Americanization' process encompassed each aspect of Yugoslavian society. Children in Yugoslavia, she argued, were identifying themselves with the American cartoons and strips of Walt Disney, adults read Western novels, Coca-Cola had widespread throughout Yugoslavia, fashion was according to the American model, the first supermarkets appeared, American products were exposed at an exhibition in Zagreb, etc. Furthermore, the establishment of jazz music in Yugoslavia began in 1958 with the first jazz radio shows in Belgrade, Zagreb, and Ljubljana.⁶¹ The first traces of rock and roll in Yugoslavia can be seen in 1956 when the sounds of Elvis Presley, Fats Domino, Pat Boone, etc. begin to play. Since 1960, Rock and roll have begun to break into the public eye and has attracted increasing attention. From a 1968 report by the Ford foundation officer Edward F. D'Arms, we learn that art institutions in that year were stronger than ever before, that they provided better and more systematic instruction, and that they provided careers for their best graduates.⁶² The significant artistic orientation of Yugoslavia towards the West significantly contributed to this, with the help of Ford's grants for the education and training of artists. Overall, the consequences of the American public and private programs have brought Yugoslav culture much closer to Western values.

Western influence on communist intellectual circles

The first organized resistance against communism began at the beginning of the Cold war with the US confrontation against this ideology. One of the ongoing concerns the U.S. government faced year after year during the 1950s was possibly increasing communist influence among students and intellectuals outside the territory of the Soviet Union. One of the steps taken by the CIA in the early 1950s to weaken communist influence was to be counteroffensive against Moscow-sponsored organizations by providing alternatives to various constituencies: intellectual, labor, youth, and students;⁶³ In its effort, the CIA transformed America's National Student Association into an intelligence asset during the Cold War, using students, knowingly and unknowingly, as agents within the United States and abroad. At its height in the early 1960s, the National Student Association (NSA) had a million students as members and was spread over 400 university campuses. The NSA was one of the largest and most influential student organizations in the United States, funded and largely controlled by the Central Intelligence Agency.⁶⁴ In his study, Paget cited the observation of CIA Director Dulles on the role that the NSA played in the course of the Cold War: We got everything we wanted. I think what we did was worth every penny. If we turned back the communists and made them milder and easier to live with, it was because we stopped them in certain areas, and the student area was one of them.⁶⁵

Also, the U.S. government has initiated a more intensive distribution of American literature worldwide, including books and periodicals, intensifying exchanges and meetings and establishing pro-Western associations among intellectuals. For this reason, the Psychological Strategy Board of the US government in 1953 developed a doctrine to combat this problem.⁶⁶ Communists carefully selected this target group (students and intellectuals) because they influenced policy and the creation of public opinion in underdeveloped areas and the fact that intellectuals had a huge impact on young people. Their ideological campaign during the 1950s consisted of distributing literature that supported major communist themes, many cultural

activities, as well as exchange programs.⁶⁷ Communists, like Americans, used the program of exchanging people, especially students, professors, and artists, to increase their influence among students and intellectuals. In 1953, the Soviet exchange program included 45,000 people.⁶⁸

The main weakness of the American approach to students and intellectuals in various parts of the world was that the information materials at the time were not in line with the wishes and interests of the intellectual audience. Radio programs did not seriously influence foreign intellectuals who also did not show much interest in the then-American bulletins and releases.⁶⁹ The content of American propaganda material from the early 1950s itself was not at the level of intellectual proportions, so these groups viewed the average periodical literature below their dignity. As usual, students and intellectuals aspired to academic literature or highly intellectual materials, especially books that they could criticize, analyze, and use for their own needs. In this field, the Americans did not offer a worthy counter-resistance to the Soviet approach at the beginning of the Cold War. For that reason, it was decided that intellectuals should be treated as a distinct group due to their important position in society.

As a result of communist propaganda, intellectuals were suspicious of governments in general, and the US government in particular.⁷⁰ However, the same suspicion did not exist toward American private organizations, intellectual and research organizations. In the State Department archives related to the doctrine of U.S. government coordination with private foundations and organizations to counter communist influence among students and intellectuals, we find the following statement: “Hence, the U.S. Doctrinal program should, as a major aspect of its development, ensure that non-governmental organizations, scholarly, research, fraternal, etc., which might contribute to the influencing of students and intellectuals, are stimulated to contribute to this effort. The Ford Foundation is only one of the numerous avenues of non-governmental enterprise which should be explored”.⁷¹ The main goal of involving private foundations such as the Ford Foundation in ideological conflict was solely to weaken communist influence in various states, which is confirmed in the State Department archive: The U.S. Doctrinal program released on June 29, 1953, concluded that in the effort to reduce communist

influence among students and intellectuals, private foundations, learned and professional societies, and other non-government groups be stimulated to contribute their specialized efforts.⁷²

The US government became involved in spreading influence among student circles in response to existing Soviet propaganda. It was a severe operation because intelligent and well-trained communists had long occupied the field. To achieve more effective results on the ground, the State Department has included private foundations such as Rockefeller and Ford in the doctrine of the fight against communism, using their status of 'neutrality' among foreign countries. In addition, intellectual circles in the backward areas of the world were frustrated by the socio-economic conditions in their countries, which contributed to them being more susceptible to the ideas of the communist revolution, social equality, etc. At the beginning of the Cold War, the US government could not directly influence and improve social and economic conditions in a specific area. Still, through their international contacts and experience, foundations and specific private organizations could contribute to severe changes and support the local population. Through their professionalism and influential projects in various countries, these American organizations have gained more and more trust among the local population. Therefore, it is not surprising that the authorities in Yugoslavia, as the ordinary people, were enthusiastic about the activities of American foundations and that they were, in fact, a precursor and a vital link in serious cultural programs and intellectual activities.

In overall cultural diplomacy during the 1950s and 1960s, the U.S. government relied heavily on private institutions.⁷³ Private organizations, such as foundations, professional organizations, and universities, were pioneers of American cultural interaction with other nations and were an indispensable factors in American cultural diplomacy.⁷⁴ Because of their insights on the ground, the Rockefeller and Ford foundations were very concerned about the threat of a nuclear war. Beginning in 1956 and continuing for nearly a decade, the Ford Foundation has invested \$1.8 million in two major centers of nuclear physics in Europe: *CERN*, the European Organization for Nuclear Research in Geneva (\$1.15 million); and Niels Bohr's Institute for

Theoretical Physics in Copenhagen (\$650,000);⁷⁵ In addition to the importance of promoting scientific research, the Ford Foundation viewed the centers in Geneva and Copenhagen as great locations for promoting democracy and undermining negative stereotypes about the United States.⁷⁶

The Ford Foundation and Cultural Relations with Europe during the Cold War

Although Europeans were aware of the importance of the Marshall Plan for recovery after World War II, American prestige in Europe was declining. The diplomatic missions of America did not have enough capacity and support from Washington to sufficiently develop relations in the political and social circles of Britain, France, Germany, and Italy. This was especially true of European leftists and intellectuals whose role in these societies was significant. On the other hand, the American foundations Rockefeller, Ford, and Carnegie, although they could not completely replace the official policy of Washington, were in a strategic position to act. Their work was highly regarded in European circles, so one report said the Ford Foundation was valued even in the extreme leftist circles of the British Labor Party, the German SPD, and many intellectuals in France.⁷⁷ The task of the foundations was to break down the stereotypes that Europeans had about America, its society and culture. For this reason, Shepard Stone suggested in 1954 that the Ford Foundation ‘in the interests of the United States through its own program should start making grants in France, England, and other European countries, not excluding Yugoslavia’.⁷⁸

In the case of Britain, Stone felt the need to overcome the lack of confidence in American maturity and fears of “savages” in the US Congress and the Pentagon, setting the stage for the contact between British political leaders, intellectuals, and business circles with American colleagues.⁷⁹ In France, the foundation sought to help modernize life and build understanding with the United States. One of the steps was to initiate a project with Paris sociology professor

Raymond Aron on analyzing the French political elite, their attitudes, and influences in Europe.⁸⁰ In Germany and Italy, the foundation has invested heavily in strengthening democratic political and economic institutions, and in the educational fields of political science and sociology.⁸¹ Ford Foundation officials did not ignore and omit Yugoslavia in their activities and visits, considering it extremely important for American national interests.

Although the American government was very present with the activities in the diplomatic field in Europe, the official policy indicated the withdrawal from the cultural front. It was a space that the Ford Foundation and other private American organizations filled. The director of the international program of the Stone Foundation was very familiar with the deep reservations of Europeans about American culture, negative opinions about trash and vulgar American music, etc. For that reason, the task of the foundation was to acquaint Europeans with excellent American educational institutions, scientific and research institutes, museums, writers, musicians, and artists. Stone believed that many Europeans have unjust prejudices against American society and culture. The Ford Foundation invested heavily in sending American plays, artists, and orchestras to Europe during this period.

The American ambassadors to Europe, aware of the capacity and intentions of the Ford Foundation, sent requests for financial support to projects in the field of culture. For example, the American ambassador in Belgrade sent a strong request to the Ford Foundation to send Porgy and Bess⁸² to Yugoslavia, emphasizing that such a visit will have astonishing political and psychological results on the ground.⁸³ Also, in the mid-1950s, U.S. Ambassador to Paris Dillon strongly urged the Ford Foundation to support the U.S. Art Festival in Paris believing that such cultural content could have strong political effects.⁸⁴

Numerous visits, connections, and knowledge of social and political opportunities in Europe have contributed to Stone's strong interest in supporting the Congress for Cultural Freedom, considering it 'the most effective organization in Europe working among political,

intellectual and cultural leaders'.⁸⁵ Like many CCF members, Stone also belonged to an elite that had a deep conviction of the need to unite Americans and Europeans into a so-called Atlantic community and culture.⁸⁶ Stone, therefore, believed that Europe and America, in addition to common military and economic interest against the Soviet Union, also had a common intellectual and historical heritage. Aware of the stereotypes present among Europeans about his country, Stone believed that Americans must wage two cultural wars, one against the Soviet bloc, although he believed it was being won in the 1950s, and the other against Western European perceptions of American culture, which according to him was a more complicated challenge.⁸⁷ During the Cold War, constant information from the field gave Ford Foundation officials a clear signal that people in Eastern Europe were showing a longing and tendency toward Western culture, languages, education, and living standards, positively affecting Ston's confidence in American or Western culture dominance against the Soviet bloc.

As early as 1954, Stone proposed to the Ford Foundation's board of directors to consider financial support for the activities of Congress for Cultural Freedom; to consider the exchange of leaders (influential people in European societies) including cultural leaders; and to consider sending American art exhibitions and theater and music groups to major European centers.⁸⁸ In the bureaucratic structure of the Ford Foundation, Stone had confrontations with colleagues who did not have the support of the Foundation's commitment to Europe, given its limited financial resources. However, with the support of his mentor John McCloy, who was a member of the Foundation's board of directors and chairman of the Council on Foreign Relations, he put many ideas into practice.

3 YUGOSLAV EXCHANGE PROGRAM OF THE FORD FOUNDATION

The Ford Foundation's exchange program in Yugoslavia began in 1958, although their contact with the Yugoslav authorities started much earlier. The foundation's archives reveal that officials from Yugoslavia contacted the Ford Foundation in 1953 to investigate whether they

would be interested in launching activities in Yugoslavia.⁸⁹ After a series of visits, talks, as well as negotiations on common objectives and methods of the program, the Yugoslav Exchange Program was initiated in the fall of 1958.⁹⁰ Ford Program in Yugoslavia was launched to enable qualified individuals from the government sector, academia, and culture to meet, study, and (or) work with colleagues in the United States or Western Europe. The program was designed to strengthen ties with Yugoslavia and exchange ideas and opinions in the field of social sciences and humanities in particular.⁹¹ At the same time, the project program allowed American leaders and researchers to visit Yugoslavia for a brief observation or lecture. Still, the focus was unquestionably on Yugoslavs and their exposure to Western culture and ideology.

One of the examples of concrete talks between Yugoslav officials and the Ford Foundation took place during the stay of Dr. Vilfan, the Secretary-General to President Tito of Yugoslavia, during his visit to the United States for personal medical reasons. He met with Mr. Shepard Stone, a Ford Foundation official, wondering why the Ford Foundation did not launch its program in Yugoslavia. Vilfan revealed that the Yugoslav leadership was impressed by the Foundation's activities in Poland and that Yugoslavia was eager to cooperate with and support the Foundation in launching activities in its territory.⁹² It is believed that Ford's enterprise in Poland was the first major effort undertaken by an American institution to open channels into Eastern Europe.⁹³ Yugoslav scientists who wanted to go abroad for education, training or visits were forced to seek help from foreign agencies. Although they were not handicapped by lack of money, Ford foundation official Edward D'arms stated in his 1955 analysis that they still did not own foreign currency to buy books or equipment.⁹⁴ No Yugoslav, except with a special permit, could buy the equivalent of \$ 10 of foreign currency to travel abroad.⁹⁵

An American delegation led by Mr. Nielsen of the Ford Foundation, Princeton University President Robert Goheen and Dean Harlan Cleveland of Syracuse University visited Yugoslavia in October 1958 to negotiate an exchange project with the Belgrade government, analyze higher

education in Yugoslavia, and interview candidates for the school year 1959-1960.⁹⁶ Under Yugoslav law, all candidates had to be screened by an education commission chaired by Rector Blagojevic of the University of Belgrade.⁹⁷ Twenty four candidates who also represented the five largest universities in Yugoslavia (Beograd, Zagreb, Sarajevo, Ljubljana, Skoplje) were selected to come to the United States in 1959-1960.⁹⁸ In the following academic year, 1960, the Ford Foundation was even more organized in Yugoslavia and divided all grant candidates into 3 groups in the following order: Leaders (Group A), Research Scholars (Group B), and Specialists (Group C).⁹⁹

Table 1. Ford grantees from Yugoslavia invited in 1959.

FORD GRANTEES – INVITED 1959			
Name and Surname	Title	Field	Grant
Ljubivoje ACIMOVIC	Scientific Researcher, Institute of International Politics and Economics in Belgrade	International Law (International Organizations)	1 year
Aleksander BAJT	Professor of Economics, University of Ljubljana	Economics (rate of investment)	1 year
Borislav BLAGOJEVIC	Rector of University of Belgrade	Comparative law (higher education)	45 days
Marian BLEJEC	Professor of Economics, University of Ljubljana	Economics (statistics)	1 year
Olivera BURIC	Assistant at the Institute of Social Sciences, Belgrade	Sociology (family relations)	1 month
Dusan CALIC	Chairman of the Economic Committee of the Croatian Parliament	Economics (industrial productivity)	6 months
Jovan DJORDJEVIC	Director of the Institute of Social Sciences, State Undersecretary of Federal Executive Council	Political Science	5 months
Dan GJANKOVIC	Professor at Law Faculty, University of Zagreb	Constitutional law	1 year
Joze GORICAR	Professor of Sociology, University of Ljubljana, Member of Council of Education	Sociology of law	3 months

	at Republic Level		
Vladimir IBLER	Professor at Law Faculty, University of Zagreb	International Law (territorial waters)	1 year
Petar IVICEVIC	Undersecretary of State, Chief of Cabinet of the Vice President of the Federal Executive Council.	Public administration	2 months
Samuel KAMHI	Pro-rector of Sarajevo University and Dean of Law Faculty	Law (civil law and jury system)	6 months
Ivan LAVRAC	Professor at Faculty of Economics, Ljubljana University	Economics (history of economic theory)	1 year
Oleg MANDIC	Professor of Sociology, Zagreb University	Sociology (changing social stratification)	1 year
Naum NAUMOUSKI	Mayor of Skopje	Public administration	2 months
Nikola SRZENTIC	Undersecretary of State, Secretary of Judiciary	Criminal law	3 months
Rados STAMENKO VIC	Professor of Economics at the Institute of Social Sciences, Belgrade	Economics	5 months
Janez Stanonik	Head of Department of English language, Ljubljana University	English and American literature	1 year
Dusan STEFANOVI C	Counselor at the Federal Institute for Town Planning and Housing in Belgrade	Economics (urbanization and economic planning)	8 months
Nikola UZUNOV	Docent at Faculty of Economics, Skopje University	Economics (economics of underdeveloped countries)	5 months
Uros VIDOVIC	Assistant to the Federal Secretary of Finance	Economics (Financial problems and fiscal and monetary policy)	5 months
Djuro KUREPA	Professor of Mathematics, University of Zagreb	Advanced Mathematics	/
Mladen CALDAROVI C	Editor in Chief of 'Pregled' ¹⁰⁰	Sociology of Education	1 year

(Ford Foundation Archives, International Affairs Records, FA748, Exchanges Series V, Box 7, Folder Title: Yugoslavian Program – Reports, Dates: 1959-1969)

Table 2. Statistical summary of the Ford program by field (1959-1962).

Total number	Field	Acad.	Non-acad.	Acad.	Non-acad.	Acad.	Non-acad.	Acad.	Non-acad.
31	Economics	6	2	8	1	6	2	5	1
11	Political Science	2	2	2	1	1	0	3	0
9	Philosophy / Psychology	0	0	2	0	4	0	3	0
7	Sociology	4	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
6	Law	4	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
5	Education	1	0	2	0	2	0	0	0
5	English / American Literature	1	0	1	0	0	0	3	0
4	Cultural relations / Art	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	1
2	Medicine / Health	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
1	Mathematics	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

(Ford Foundation, International Affairs Record, Exchanges, Series V, Box 7, Folder Title: Yugoslavian program- background)

The first initial years of the Ford Foundation's experience with the Yugoslav exchange program have been satisfactory.¹⁰¹ The management of the foundation was satisfied with overcoming administrative difficulties in bringing candidates to the United States, emphasizing that their quality (scholarship holders) was high. However, in the evaluation report from 1961, the manager of the Ford Foundation stated the impression that, for some reason, the foundation does not reach precisely the total number of qualified candidates from Yugoslavia.¹⁰² This was linked to the Yugoslav Educational Commission, with a mandate of screening all potential candidates for Ford's scholarships before entering the interview process. Nevertheless, the foundation resolutely continued its activities in Yugoslavia in the years to come. Ford's cooperation with the Yugoslav Commission was at a high level, as stated by a member of the

foundation's delegation, Mr. Campbell, who claimed that the procedures set by the Yugoslav Commission as well as the general quality of the interviewed candidates were even higher than his mission in Poland.¹⁰³

The table above shows the foundation's almost total orientation toward the social sciences with a strong emphasis on investing in economics, political science, and sociology. One significant change in the scholarship process for Yugoslav candidates is that after 1962, the foundation reserved seats for candidates in culture and the arts. So, their number has dramatically increased. Despite the increase in the number of fellows in the areas of culture and skills, a field that required special treatment in the form of selections and the actual stay in the United States, some candidates acted negligently in improving their English-speaking skills. Still, most of them were highly motivated and showed efforts to improve their English, which ultimately enriched their stay in the United States. As a fellow, Boris Grabnar, Editor of Cultural and Educational programs at Radio-Television Ljubljana, had a very diverse and rich program in the United States. He met many scriptwriters, editors, and playwrights of television in New York, attended a science-fiction writer's annual meeting in Washington, had a lengthy visit to the Department of Mass Communication and Theater Arts at the University of California, visited television producing centers in California, and visited workshops of educational and commercial television, etc.¹⁰⁴ His fellowship ended with the ability to fluently speak English as well as a large number of contacts, both professional and private.¹⁰⁵

Another fellow Stevan Majstorovic, a former editor-in-chief of cultural weekly magazine 'Danas' in Serbia, also had the opportunity to meet a large number of editors, writers, people working on educational television, actors, playwrights, directors.¹⁰⁶ Because of his great interest in American culture and literature, he attended classes in American literature and Sociology of Culture at New York University and visited some TV production centers and theater rehearsals, experimental and repertory too.¹⁰⁷ He also had the opportunity to travel through the United States visiting Chapel Hill, New Orleans, Houston, Dallas, Tulsa (Museum of Indian Art), Santa Fe, Los Angeles, Santa Barbara (Center for the Study of Democratic Institutions), Berkeley, San

Francisco, Salt Lake City, Denver, Chicago and Boston.¹⁰⁸ He spent most of his stay at the University of California, Berkeley, attending lectures and seminars related to contemporary American literature.¹⁰⁹

As can be seen from Mr. Grabnar and Mr. Majstorovic, a vibrant and busy schedule had a great precondition for cultural effects on the candidates. Also, the Ford Foundation managed to attract people who worked in critical positions in the field of culture and art in Yugoslavia. Some of those were: Director of Modern Museum in Belgrade, Editor in cultural and educational programs at Radio-Television Ljubljana, Advisor to the Commission on Art and Culture of Serbia, Counselor for Art Education in Zagreb, etc.¹¹⁰ The fact that the most significant number of American scholarships in the late 1950s and 1960s in Yugoslavia was in the field of social sciences indicates the intention of the United States to influence the creation of the Yugoslav elite, which through influence on public opinion, had an impact on overall social consciousness in Yugoslavia.¹¹¹ Many Yugoslav scholars who resided in the United States became significant individuals who left a substantial impact on Yugoslav politics, economics, science, culture, and the arts.¹¹²

Table 3. An overall statistical program of the Ford program in Yugoslavia by field (1959-1969).

Total number	Field	Academic	Non-academic
55	Economics	40	15
25	Art/Culture/Radio-Television/Music/Film	6	19
20	Sociology	13	7
20	Philosophy/Psychology	18	2
14	Political Science	10	4
13	English / American Literature	12	1
13	Law	11	2
10	Architecture	6	4
10	Education	8	2
8	Journalism		8
5	Engineering	5	
3	Agriculture	1	2

3	Insurance/Finance		3
2	History	2	
1	Marketing		1
1	Biology	1	
1	Geography	1	
1	Information Systems		1
1	Industrial Design	1	
1	International Law	1	
1	Library Science		1
1	Criminology		1
1	Medicine	1	

(Ford Foundation, International Affairs Record, Exchanges, Series V, Box 7, Folder Title: Yugoslavian program- background)

3.1 Leaders (Group A) – Yugoslav Exchange Program 1959-1969

The goal and intention of the foundation were for the candidates from Yugoslavia to be people of high status with a direct influence on public affairs in society and scientific and educational activities. The Ford Foundation archives testify that eligible candidates for this group were state officials, essential individuals from the sphere of science and culture, university rectors and vice-rectors from federal units, etc.¹¹³ The Ford Foundation Selection Committee worked together with the Yugoslav Education Commission to prepare a list of candidates for this purpose, and the latter also provided background information on each candidate individually. In the final selection of candidates for the group of leaders, the Ford Foundation had two specific conditions for its Commission:

1. Is his role in the Yugoslav politico-social system far-reaching and important?
2. Does he evince scholarly curiosity and flexibility of mind about the United States? i.e. Will he participate in the program with a reasonable degree of objectivity, willingness to learn, and desire to exchange ideas?¹¹⁴

The leaders' program included travel, observations, consultations with colleagues in the United States, and meetings with government officials and influential people in the fields of education and culture. Unlike research scholarships and specialists, the grant period was shorter

in most cases but hectic at the same time. Their stay in America was fully financially covered by the foundation, including an English translator (if necessary).¹¹⁵ Below is a list of Leaders who have resided in the United States under a Ford Foundation grant, including their sphere of interest and their positions. These were individuals who stayed in the United States with the permission of the Yugoslav authorities and returned to their positions upon returning to their home country.

Table 4. Ford grantees from Yugoslavia – Leaders (Group A).

Ford Grantees – Leaders (Group A)			
Name and Surname	Title	Field	Grant
Borislav BLAGOJEVIC	Rector of University of Belgrade	Comparative law (higher education)	45 days
Samuel KAMHI	Pro-rector of Sarajevo University and Dean of Law Faculty	Law (civil law and jury system)	6 months
Dusan CALIC	Chairman of the Econ Committee of the Croatian Parliament	Economics (industrial productivity)	6 months
Jovan DJORDJEVIC	Director of the Inst. of Soc. Sciences, State Undersecretary of Federal Executive Council	Political Science	5 months
Petar IVICEVIC	Undersecretary of State, Chief of Cabinet of the Vice-President of the Federal Executive Council	Public administration	2 months
Sreten BJELICIC	Director General of Yugoslav Community of Insurance, Belgrade	Insurance and Finance	10 mont
Naum NAUMOUSKI	Mayor of Skopje	Public administration	2 months
Nikola SRZENTIC	Undersecretary of State, Secretary of Judiciary	Criminal law	3 months
Joze GORICAR	Professor of Sociology, Univ of Ljubljana, Member of C. of Edu.	Sociology of law	3 months
Dusan KANAZIR	Head of Biochemistry Dep, Institute for Nuclear Science, Belgrade	Molecular biology / radiobiology	1 month
Petar IVICEVIC	Undersecretary of State, Chief of Cabinet of the V. Pres. of the F.E.C.	Public administration	2 months
Arsen JOVANOVIC	Institute for International Politics and Economy, Belgrade	Industrial Sociology	8 months
Dragutin FRANKOVIC	Yugoslav Institute for Educational Research, Belgrade	Education	4 months
Dusan VEJNOVIC	Committee for Cultural Relations with Foreign Countries, Bel	Cultural Exchanges	13 months
Naum NAUMOUSKI	Mayor of Skopje	Public administration	2 months
Nikola SRZENTIC	Undersecretary of State, Secretary of Judiciary	Criminal law	3 months
Zdravko VUKOVIC	Sec of the Council of Educ of Peoples Rep of Serbia	Education	4 months
Trajca GRUJOSKI	Secretary, Executive Council of Macedonia	Municipal Government	4 months
Bozidar DJORDJEVIC	Pro-rector and Dean, Medical Faculty, Belgrade University	Medicine-cardiology	4 months

C			
Marijan HORVAT	Pro-rector and professor, Law Faculty, University of Zagreb	University administration and Roman law	4 months
Dusanka KOVACEVIC	President of the Council for Education of the Republic BiH, Deputy in the Federal Assembly	Education (org of the school system)	4 months
Milovan MATIC	Sec for Yugoslav National Commission for UNESCO	International cultural relations	4 months
Kemal Sejfula	Secretary of Finance, Executive Council of Macedonia	Finance and Taxation	4 months
Dolfe VOGELNIK	Pro-rector, University of Ljubljana	Demography	6 months
Nikola Vuco	Dean, Faculty of Economics, University of Belgrade	History of Political Economy	6 mont
Rikard LANG	Dean, Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb	Economics (automation)	6 mont

(Ford foundation archive, International Affairs records, Yugoslavian Program-Reports, 1959-1969)

In practical terms, Rector Blagojevic from Belgrade University visited various universities, technical schools, and scientific institutes during his stay, including two days at Harvard and five days in Washington D.C.¹¹⁶ Although his stay, unlike other candidates in this group, was short, in the confidential evaluation of Ford's grantees, Blagojevic was highly praised by the foundation: 'an absolute dynamo of energy and inexhaustible capacity for work. He utilized every minute of his visit here to learn as much as possible about the administration in education.'¹¹⁷ Besides Blagojevic, many other candidates also impressed by the foundation's attitude toward grants. Dusan Calic, an economist in the field of industrial productivity, was, according to the foundation, very impressed with the assistance and information he was given at all the companies that he visited and back in Yugoslavia was one of the most enthusiastic supporters of the Ford Program and IIE's handling of it.¹¹⁸ Samuel Kamhi, the vice-rector of Sarajevo University, has shown great interest in the US civil jury system and education structure. In practical terms, he was impressed with school objects, classrooms, and other facilities when visiting a school in Washington, Connecticut. On his return home, he gave speeches on the topic

of his lived experience and remained an intellectual with a deep and continuous interest in the United States.¹¹⁹

It was evident that the Ford Foundation wanted to use these programs to encourage Yugoslav intellectuals and officials to understand and approach American theories, problem-solving, and moral values. The foundation monitored scholars from all groups on their return to Yugoslavia. Thus, it is recorded that Professor Ivan Lavrac was of a very disciplined mind and able to absorb a great deal of western theory of economics.¹²⁰ In addition, the foundation noted a detail from the defense of a candidate's dissertation at a Yugoslav university where Professor Lavrac was a member of the commission, arguing that his comments and questions indicated that he was trying to reconcile the Marxist view of the economy with Western theorists.¹²¹ On the other hand, the foundation also had experience with candidates who were not interested in expanding their knowledge and connections during their stay in the United States.

3.2 Research Scholars and Specialists (Group B and C)

Under the term research scholarship, the foundation took into account professors, university assistants, and graduate students. Therefore, their stay and work in the United States were primarily attached to universities. The mental and physical health of the candidates was one of the prerequisites; younger candidates were preferred. In most cases, the candidates had to have a degree from a recognized higher education institution, and the candidate had to have an excellent working knowledge of English. For those who needed additional language training, the foundation allowed them to start their fellowships during the summer to bring their English to the desired level before the academic year. Compared to their colleagues from Poland, the Ford Foundation noticed that the candidates from Yugoslavia were not so interested in learning English before coming to the United States. From the perspective of the foundation, the tendency was for the candidates to wait for the arrival at the destination and then, with strong motivation, work seriously on improving the English language at the expense of scientific or academic

achievement.¹²² The general length of the program for candidates from the research scholarship group was one academic year.

Candidates under the group of specialists were also the focus of the Ford Foundation program because of their profession or the nature of the discipline. The foundation has defined such individuals as professionals in non-academic fields per se, such as journalism, architecture, industrial management, practical arts, etc. The only difference in grants compared to research scholarships was the length of their stay in the United States because they received grants ranging from three to six months.¹²³

4 FORD IN YUGOSLAVIA AND AMERICAN FOREIGN POLICY

Since its expulsion from the communist bloc in 1948, Yugoslavia, with the help of Western aid programs, has emerged from economic backwardness and become a politically stable nation that differed significantly with certain aspects of liberalization at the social and administrative level from other communist states. Administrative liberalization also referred to the greater rights of federal republics within the union. However, this process of decentralization did not affect the dominant position of the Communist Party in Yugoslavia. In the early 1960s, the Yugoslav elite faced apathy toward communism, especially among the younger population, who were increasingly influenced by Western materialist standards and cultural influences.¹²⁴ The Ford Foundation often sent envoys to Yugoslavia to investigate the situation on the ground. This was especially true in the period in which the foundation initiated the process of educational exchange.

The communist authorities in Yugoslavia viewed the Ford Foundation as a neutral player without an ideological background. However, as Larry Schwartz stated in his analysis of the relationship between the Ford Foundation and the CIA during the early stages of the Cold War: “Unquestionably, the Ford foundation trustees and officers, as part of the American ruling elite, shared the prevailing, anti-Communist Cold war assumptions in support of American

hegemony”.¹²⁵ From the very beginning of their activities at the international level, high officials of the Ford Foundation were very close to the governing structures of the American administration. The influence of foundations on American foreign policy was manifested, among other things, through the frequent appointment of State Department officials for the affairs of foundations and the recurring appointment of foundation officials to the matters of the State Department. Thus, the president of the Ford Foundation between 1950 and 1953, Paul Hoffman, was highly regarded by President Truman as a person with the experience of spending a considerable amount of money on social purposes.¹²⁶ He was elected by President Truman to lead the European Cooperation Administration (ECA) and to oversee the implementation of the Marshall Plan in the precariously post-war period in Europe.¹²⁷ After World War II, the director of the Ford Foundation's international affairs department from 1952-1967, Shepard Stone, was selected by the US High Commissioner John McCloy as Assistant Director for Public Affairs for occupied Germany and was later promoted to director. John J. McCloy was a vital member of the foreign policy establishment and a prominent adviser to American presidents from Franklin D. Roosevelt to Ronald Reagan. He served as Assistant Secretary of War during World War II. In the period after 1945 served as President of the World Bank, American High Commissioner for Germany, and Chairman of the Council on Foreign Relations. In addition to all of the above positions, John J. McCloy was a board member of the Ford Foundation. In Ford's central archives, we find the guidelines for the Foundation's activities in Yugoslavia, the most important of which is the following: “The Foundation should approve no project unless it has the full support of the American ambassador in Belgrade and officials of the State Department and particular other U.S. government agencies”.¹²⁸

As for the selection of candidates for American grants, the Ford Foundation had a joint strategy with the American government to select the Yugoslavs. This is evidenced by an interview with Professor Roglić in 1960 (Chairman of the Department of Geography at the University in Zagreb and former fellow at the Universities of Chicago and Texas), in which he stated: “... party members (from Yugoslavia) will go to the United States under the present Ford fellowship program. Although an opponent of the communist party in Yugoslavia, I believe this

is all for good. Communists will suffer if they try to monopolize fellowship appointments. The mixed committee currently makes these appointments of representatives from Ford and the government".¹²⁹ The general strategy and operational activities of the Ford Foundation in Yugoslavia during the 1950s and 1960s were in line with the interests of American foreign policy in this area. The common goal of the Ford Foundation and the American government was the orientation of Yugoslavia towards the Western world and the strengthening of ties. Accordingly, the focus on social science programs was to distract Yugoslavs from the ideology of communism.

5 FORD FOUNDATION'S FIELD REPORTS FROM YUGOSLAVIA

A various officials and other members of the delegations wrote reports that gave the Ford foundation a clear picture of the program's success in this country and the reactions of the people on the ground. All the field reports we encountered confirm that the activities of the Ford Foundation in Yugoslavia were a very successful project. One of such was prepared by Ford's delegate John Fischer in 1961, in which he observed that the Yugoslav project is, in his words, 'well worthwhile and should be continued'.¹³⁰ He claimed that Ford's scholarship program did not compete with other programs. Moreover, it was an essential addition to similar programs run by the US government. For example, among those selected for Group 'A' in 1961 (leaders from Yugoslavia) of the Ford Foundation were three people whom the American Embassy in Belgrade wanted to send to America but, for political reasons, was unable to approach.¹³¹

Ford delegate Fischer highlighted a general excitement among younger but also established individuals to participate in scientific research or professional work in the United States or Western Europe.¹³² This meant that the foundation had great merits in the ideological inclination of the Yugoslavs, especially the educated ones, towards the West. A complete turn of the entire Yugoslav policy was not expected in a short period, but it was, according to the foundation

‘basically a slow process of education and change...’¹³³ It is worth mentioning that Ford Foundation received several requests from the Yugoslav Education Commission and Yugoslav government officials to modify Ford’s scholarship program to include engineering and research staff scholarships. Still, in correspondence with the State Department, the Ford Foundation had different intentions. Concerning the scope of scholarships and type of programs, John Fischer argued:

*“The Yugoslav government obviously has good reasons, from its point of view, for wanting to send more technologists abroad for training – but on this point the government’s interests do not seem to coincide with the interests of the United States or the Ford Foundation. From our point of view, it is highly desirable to expose future political leaders, economists, journalists and teachers of the humanities to some experience of American life.”*¹³⁴

The Ford Foundation viewed its presence in Yugoslavia (and Eastern Europe) as an extended challenge and commitment. A report prepared by Ford delegate Herb Passin stated: “It was almost the unanimous view of the people I spoke to, including many non-communists, that the only real possibility of change in the next period is in the higher ranks of the Party”.¹³⁵ Due to this fact, the foundation almost inevitably targeted high-ranking party officials in its activities, bearing in mind the possibility of ideological influence on them, primarily due to their influence in the state. In general, the Ford foundation’s approach to Yugoslavia was as follows:

1. To make a big campaign to keep in touch with Yugoslav intellectuals.
 2. To invite as many as possible to its activities, partly to give them a chance to get out of the country, and partly to associate them with the foundation.
 3. To aim at three different groups:
-

a) Non-communists; b) younger Party high-ups; c) the generation that will be in leadership ten years from now;¹³⁶

As for the non-communists, the Ford Foundation felt a moral obligation to help. The strategy was to pull non-communists under grants out of the country for education and to build their international prestige to make them more secure and influential at home. Many of the foundation's fellows testified how international acquaintances helped them immensely. Not many cases have been reported of Ford Foundation scholarship holders being hindered in their academic or career advancement due to schooling in the West. To have a more diversified group of candidates, the foundation targeted the younger generation of the Party. In specific cases, the foundation deliberately sent party men and non-communists together in a joint program so that the party member could see how accepted and well-regarded the other is.¹³⁷ The generation of politicians and intellectuals that was expected to take the lead in the decade that followed was crucial for any activity of the foundation in Yugoslavia.¹³⁸

In his observation during January and February 1962, Howard R. Bowen stated: "...I think there is here more human and less dogmatic communism than in Russia or, especially, than in China.. We are impressed by the degree of intellectual freedom, by the trends towards pluralism in the society, and by the interests in application western ideas to Yugoslavian problems. Among the candidates are a surprising members of women. It is clear that the status of professional woman in Yugoslavia is very good, generally on a par with that of man".¹³⁹ Another Ford envoy, Richard B. Neustadt, in 1962 recorded experiences from a conversation with a former fellow named Trišković, an Economist at the Federal Planning Bureau of Yugoslavia at the time, in which he claimed: "One thing I learned in the States is that there's no limit to consumer demand; once it starts it goes right through the roof; the more people have the more they want;"¹⁴⁰ Because of these experiences, Neustadt was convinced that the Ford Foundation was on the right track when it comes to Yugoslavia. He observed: "When able younger man, strategically located in Yugoslav society, gain insights of this sort from exposure to the States – insights with utility and meaning for their work and thought at home; insights which they might miss if they had

stayed at home – your program (Ford) is justified, so far as I am concerned. No matter what they do with what they learn, the great thing is to feed their streak of realism and empiricism. The great thing is to make such ‘coming man’ at once more adapt and more worldly than before”.¹⁴¹

Professor Irwin T. Sanders visited Yugoslavia in 1964 to address an exchange program between Boston University and the University of Skopje that was interrupted by the 1963 Skopje earthquake.¹⁴² On that occasion, Professor Sanders had the opportunity to talk informally with Yugoslavs about Ford’s scholarship project and inform the foundation officials about general reactions. Talking to people from different backgrounds, he was greatly surprised by the popularity and positive reactions of people to Ford’s scholarship program, which, according to his analysis was an ‘overwhelming success’.¹⁴³ One of the people he met was a high-ranking Macedonian politician Kemal Sejfula¹⁴⁴, one of the Ford Foundation scholarship holders who claimed to know of no Ford scholarship holder who did not return with positive feelings towards the United States.¹⁴⁵ Sejfula was also one of the members of the Communist Party who spread a very positive image of America and its system in which he had the opportunity to reside. In his words: “I told them (to his colleagues), that you will say I am making propaganda for the Americans but it is important for us to know that we are not getting the correct picture of America through our information media”.¹⁴⁶

The impact of American scholarships on the people of Yugoslavia had two dimensions. The first dimension was the personal progress of scholarship holders in Yugoslav society through the occupation of high positions. The second related to the impact that the fellows had on their environment upon their return to Yugoslavia, as can be seen from the testimony of Prof. Sanders: “Both in Belgrade and Zagreb I was told that the individual scholars’ outlook was almost always changed – usually broadened- by US experience and that this was having a perceptible influence on the intellectual life in both cities”.¹⁴⁷ One former fellow (Ford foundation) regarding economic field phrased: “Our economists (Yugoslavian) have no idea of

what a developed economy is really like until they visit the United States. They learn that many of their former assumptions were wrong”.¹⁴⁸ Another grantee stated, and he was an ardent party member: “The United States is what we hope our socialist economy can become. There all one’s want can be supplied”.¹⁴⁹

As a representative of the Ford Foundation, in 1964, Natasha Deakin had an opportunity to meet 28 old scholarship grantees and 52 new scholarship grantees of the foundation during a five-week visit to Yugoslavia. In her observation, she noticed that: “most of them speak English better now than they did when they left the United States. They are also happier about their vacation in our country than they were at their departure...All of them have higher status and more responsible positions now”.¹⁵⁰

The Ford Foundation has been very professional in its tenure and has had a well-developed intellectual network of experts in the United States and Yugoslavia. Due to its professionalism in the field and the provision of quality services, the foundation had the opportunity to influence administrative policies in certain countries. In a letter to the Chairman of the Ford Foundation, professor of economics James E. Howell from Stanford University, as a member of the Ford delegation, outlined his experiences during a 1967 visit to Yugoslavia.¹⁵¹ The visit was aimed at assisting the Yugoslav commission during the period of economic reform and providing analysis to the management educational project in Yugoslavia.¹⁵² In the mid-1960s, the Yugoslavian state was in a period of economic development which automatically required the systematic improvement of management in theory and practice, as well as the reorganization of rich state resources and levels of productivity. Because of their expertise and the trust built in Yugoslav officials, Ford’s delegation led by Professor Howell in 1967 directly assisted the domestic commission in drafting the economic master plan at the federal level.¹⁵³

Such a plan required additional decentralization of the economy and greater reliance on independent competitive enterprises. It was emphasized that it would be of great help to have US

assistance in drafting this plan from the outset. More precisely, the members of the Yugoslav commission directly recommended and targeted the aid of the Ford Foundation with the role of providing an expert consultant for this purpose. The reform measures suggested by the Ford delegation included turning the Yugoslavian economy more to the direction of the market, further decentralization and reliance on independent competitive enterprises, cultivation of management and fuller enterprise decisions in industries, and attempts to attain a convertible currency in international markets.¹⁵⁴ In this way, the foundation had a direct insight into the political and economic events in the country and the opportunity to strengthen the position of the American interests in the international field with its proposals.

6 CONCLUSION

The arrival of the Ford foundation in Yugoslavia was initiated by the Yugoslav leadership. Although excluded from the communist bureau, the Yugoslav elite closely followed events in Eastern Europe. The Yugoslav elite was impressed by the activities of the Ford and Rockefeller Foundation in Poland, which significantly influenced the invocation of the same activities in Yugoslavia. The Ford Foundation, as a forerunner in American cultural diplomacy in communist countries, had a much higher reputation than the U.S. government for launching its activities. A cooperation with the Ford served as a cover for the alleged non-aligned policy of the Yugoslav elite. Furthermore, philanthropic organizations were viewed by Yugoslav authorities as politically neutral.

As for the overall American influence on education and intellectual circles, it should be emphasized that the American social sciences had a considerable influence in Yugoslavia in the late 1950s and early 1960s. Changing the status and position of sociology as a social science in Yugoslavia was one of the most outstanding academic achievements. Previously, sociology was banned as a university subject because there was no room for 'bourgeois sociology' in academic circles. In the words of a Ford delegate: '..in the Yugoslavian situation, any move towards empirical observation free from dogma has revolutionary implications.'¹⁵⁵ One of the first

significant steps taken by the foundation was the decision of Ford Foundation chairman Waldemar A. Nielsen to send Professor Paul Lazarsfeld, the Chairman of the Department of Sociology at Columbia University, to Yugoslavia, who left a significant impression on Yugoslavs and gave a big forward push to empirical social research.¹⁵⁶ The technical aspects of American sociology: batteries, scales, tests, mathematics, etc. – were more convincing than any other. The more fellows could defend their technical competence back home, the more they could appear more ‘scientific’ or even ‘mathematical’, and the better would be their chance to win acceptance.¹⁵⁷ In this way, according to Herb’s discussion with Ford’s fellows in Yugoslavia, candidates felt that they could have an effect (influence) on the intellectual and political atmosphere in Yugoslavia.¹⁵⁸ Concerning studying empirical social sciences, the foundation also supported sending Yugoslavs to English universities, as was the case with the University of Manchester.¹⁵⁹

It is also worth mentioning that the activities of the Ford Foundation had the potential to be more successful. To some extent, the foundation’s activities with local levels in the state were limited due to a very centralized system. Thus, the Yugoslav Commission for Education, through negotiations with the foundation, imposed the conclusion that the final list of candidates interested in Ford’s exchange, study or training program in America is determined by the commission in Belgrade.¹⁶⁰ This meant that not everyone interested in American programs could have the opportunity to be interviewed by the Ford Commission. The Foundation was aware that all requests submitted by various institutions and universities for project support must go through the screening of the Yugoslav Commission.

Nevertheless, numerous influential figures from Yugoslav academic and social life were scholarship holders of the Ford Foundation. Among them were rectors and vice-rectors of Yugoslav universities, numerous professors, directors of institutes, artists, journalists, as well as civil servants. In the period 1959-1969, the Ford Foundation awarded 55 grants to Yugoslavs in the field of economics, 25 grants in the field of art, culture, radio-television, music, and film, 20 grants in the field of sociology, 20 grants in the field of philosophy and psychology, etc. Ford’s

program represented a huge financial undertaking and an unforgettable experience for Yugoslavs who were largely denied the opportunity to travel to the West. After the first few years of the program, the authorities in Yugoslavia asked the foundation to include scholarships from technical sciences in the program, which the foundation refused. In terms of its operational activity, the Ford Foundation was consciously subordinated to Washington's policy towards Yugoslavia. The joint goal of the Ford Foundation and the American government was the orientation of Yugoslavia towards the Western world and the strengthening of bilateral relations. Accordingly, the focus on social science programs was to distract Yugoslavs from the ideology of communism.

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